

Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 17

The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9789>

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*During past years author worked with **borderedmagic squares** of even number blocks. These are based on equal sums magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, etc. This type of work is an extension of classical bordered magic squares. In case of multiples of 4, the extension is made for **pandiagonal** magic squares [23]. For multiples of order 6 refer Taneja [24]. Recently, author worked on odd number multiples from 3 to 15. These are based on different sums of magic squares of orders 3 to 15 [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35]. This work is for multiples of 17. We have worked with 28 different types of magic squares of order 17. Total work is up to order 136, but due to space problems the examples given here are only up to order 51. Higher order examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with the work.*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijjtaneja@gmail.com;
Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares	3
1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples	3
1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples	3
2 Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 17	4
2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 136 and 119	12
2.2 Magic Squares of Order 51	14
3 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares	18

1 Introduction

During past years author [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 17]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [18, 19, 20, 21]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White’s web-site [1].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White’s web-site [1] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [9, 10, 1].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [29].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 5 [30].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 7 [31].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 9 [32]
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 11 [33]
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 13 [34]
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 15 [35]
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 17 [36] (This work)

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [76, 77, 65, 66, 66, 67].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 4 [23].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 6 [24].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 8 [25].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 10 [26].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 12 [27].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 14 [28].

The work on even number multiples is with equal sums blocks of magic squares. The work on odd number multiples is with different sum magic squares.

This work is for bordered magic squares multiples of 17. Here are working with 28 different types of magic square of order 17. The procedure, how these bordered magic squares are obtained is also given. Higher orders examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with this work.

2 Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 17

Let's consider following 38 magic squares of order 17.

pan	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	
2465	1	33	48	63	78	93	108	123	138	170	185	200	215	230	245	260	275	2465
2465	257	289	15	30	45	60	75	90	105	120	152	167	182	197	212	227	242	2465
2465	224	239	271	286	12	27	42	57	72	87	119	134	149	164	179	194	209	2465
2465	191	206	238	253	268	283	9	24	39	54	69	101	116	131	146	161	176	2465
2465	158	173	188	220	235	250	265	280	6	21	36	68	83	98	113	128	143	2465
2465	125	140	155	187	202	217	232	247	262	277	3	18	50	65	80	95	110	2465
2465	92	107	122	137	169	184	199	214	229	244	259	274	17	32	47	62	77	2465
2465	59	74	89	104	136	151	166	181	196	211	226	241	256	288	14	29	44	2465
2465	26	41	56	71	86	118	133	148	163	178	193	208	223	255	270	285	11	2465
2465	282	8	23	38	53	85	100	115	130	145	160	175	190	205	237	252	267	2465
2465	249	264	279	5	20	35	67	82	97	112	127	142	157	172	204	219	234	2465
2465	216	231	246	261	276	2	34	49	64	79	94	109	124	139	154	186	201	2465
2465	183	198	213	228	243	258	273	16	31	46	61	76	91	106	121	153	168	2465
2465	150	165	180	195	210	225	240	272	287	13	28	43	58	73	88	103	135	2465
2465	117	132	147	162	177	192	207	222	254	269	284	10	25	40	55	70	102	2465
2465	84	99	114	129	144	159	174	189	221	236	251	266	281	7	22	37	52	2465
2465	51	66	81	96	111	126	141	156	171	203	218	233	248	263	278	4	19	2465
1	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

2	mgc	2357	2463	2579	2393	2517	2445	2385	2241	2699	2551	2487	2411	2535	2345	2461	2571	2465
16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18	2465	
1	242	231	233	235	237	239	241	243	43	41	39	37	35	33	46	289	2465	
3	34	216	207	209	211	213	215	217	69	67	65	63	61	72	256	287	2465	
5	36	62	96	104	102	100	98	197	198	200	202	204	94	228	254	285	2465	
7	38	64	205	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	85	226	252	283	2465	
9	40	66	203	105	128	132	130	165	166	168	126	185	87	224	250	281	2465	
11	42	68	201	107	169	136	133	153	151	152	121	183	89	222	248	279	2465	
13	44	70	199	109	167	156	146	141	148	134	123	181	91	220	246	277	2465	
273	45	71	95	177	127	155	147	145	143	135	163	113	195	219	245	17	2465	
271	240	214	97	175	129	140	142	149	144	150	161	115	193	76	50	19	2465	
269	238	212	99	173	131	138	157	137	139	154	159	117	191	78	52	21	2465	
267	236	210	101	171	164	158	160	125	124	122	162	119	189	80	54	23	2465	
265	234	208	103	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	187	82	56	25	2465	
263	232	206	196	186	188	190	192	93	92	90	88	86	194	84	58	27	2465	
261	230	218	83	81	79	77	75	73	221	223	225	227	229	74	60	29	2465	
259	244	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	247	249	251	253	255	257	48	31	2465	
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

3	mgc	2264	2546	2523	2466	2402	2383	2657	2078	2629	2556	2467	2514	2386	2507	2521	2541	2465
16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18	2465	
1	218	97	120	219	106	110	220	107	108	221	96	118	222	94	119	289	2465	
3	112	225	98	121	215	99	122	213	100	111	223	101	109	224	102	287	2465	
5	105	113	217	95	114	226	93	115	227	103	116	216	104	117	214	285	2465	
7	68	232	135	69	241	125	70	242	123	71	231	133	72	229	134	283	2465	
9	127	75	233	136	65	234	137	63	235	126	73	236	124	74	237	281	2465	
11	240	128	67	230	129	76	228	130	77	238	131	66	239	132	64	279	2465	
13	38	247	150	39	256	140	40	257	138	41	246	148	42	244	149	277	2465	
273	142	45	248	151	35	249	152	33	250	141	43	251	139	44	252	17	2465	
271	255	143	37	245	144	46	243	145	47	253	146	36	254	147	34	19	2465	
269	188	82	165	189	91	155	190	92	153	191	81	163	192	79	164	21	2465	
267	157	195	83	166	185	84	167	183	85	156	193	86	154	194	87	23	2465	
265	90	158	187	80	159	196	78	160	197	88	161	186	89	162	184	25	2465	
263	203	52	180	204	61	170	205	62	168	206	51	178	207	49	179	27	2465	
261	172	210	53	181	200	54	182	198	55	171	208	56	169	209	57	29	2465	
259	60	173	202	50	174	211	48	175	212	58	176	201	59	177	199	31	2465	
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

4	mgc	2449	2353	2241	2689	2577	2433	2401	2030	2866	2561	2449	2401	2353	2577	2513	2547	2465
16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18	2465	
1	33	250	62	151	229	63	220	107	136	199	78	190	122	166	169	289	2465	
3	152	241	34	243	55	137	211	64	213	100	167	181	79	183	115	287	2465	
5	244	48	145	242	46	214	93	130	212	76	184	108	160	182	91	285	2465	
7	235	47	256	49	138	205	77	226	94	123	175	92	196	109	153	283	2465	
9	61	139	228	40	257	106	124	198	70	227	121	154	168	85	197	281	2465	
11	35	249	60	149	232	65	219	105	134	202	80	189	120	164	172	279	2465	
13	150	239	37	245	54	135	209	67	215	99	165	179	82	185	114	277	2465	
273	247	50	144	240	44	217	95	129	210	74	187	110	159	180	89	17	2465	
271	234	45	254	52	140	204	75	224	97	125	174	90	194	112	155	19	2465	
269	59	142	230	39	255	104	127	200	69	225	119	157	170	84	195	21	2465	
267	36	251	58	147	233	66	221	103	132	203	81	191	118	162	173	23	2465	
265	148	237	38	246	56	133	207	68	216	101	163	177	83	186	116	25	2465	
263	248	51	146	238	42	218	96	131	208	72	188	111	161	178	87	27	2465	
261	236	43	252	53	141	206	73	222	98	126	176	88	192	113	156	29	2465	
259	57	143	231	41	253	102	128	201	71	223	117	158	171	86	193	31	2465	
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

5	mgc	2296	2424	2264	2191	2121	2194	2279	2129	2801	2653	2730	2809	2737	2672	2510	2630	2465
16		288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18	2465
1		129	132	112	114	113	254	257	237	239	238	79	82	62	64	63	289	2465
3		109	119	124	117	131	234	244	249	242	256	59	69	74	67	81	287	2465
5		110	118	120	122	130	235	243	245	247	255	60	68	70	72	80	285	2465
7		125	123	116	121	115	250	248	241	246	240	75	73	66	71	65	283	2465
9		127	108	128	126	111	252	233	253	251	236	77	58	78	76	61	281	2465
11		104	107	87	89	88	154	157	137	139	138	204	207	187	189	188	279	2465
13		84	94	99	92	106	134	144	149	142	156	184	194	199	192	206	277	2465
273		85	93	95	97	105	135	143	145	147	155	185	193	195	197	205	17	2465
271		100	98	91	96	90	150	148	141	146	140	200	198	191	196	190	19	2465
269		102	83	103	101	86	152	133	153	151	136	202	183	203	201	186	21	2465
267		229	232	212	214	213	54	57	37	39	38	179	182	162	164	163	23	2465
265		209	219	224	217	231	34	44	49	42	56	159	169	174	167	181	25	2465
263		210	218	220	222	230	35	43	45	47	55	160	168	170	172	180	27	2465
261		225	223	216	221	215	50	48	41	46	40	175	173	166	171	165	29	2465
259		227	208	228	226	211	52	33	53	51	36	177	158	178	176	161	31	2465
272		2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274	2465
2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465																		

6	mgc	2355	2330	2440	2214	3164	1825	2769	2510	3213	1881	2919	2381	1866	2538	2364	2671	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	200	75	102	191	193	81	199	202	67	61	224	92	198	21	269	2465	
18	272	90	215	188	99	97	209	91	88	223	229	66	93	197	232	58	2465	
273	17	206	84	110	121	177	167	164	168	108	179	111	190	100	239	51	2465	
43	247	83	207	180	169	113	123	126	122	182	160	130	68	222	24	266	2465	
33	257	189	101	174	116	153	134	148	150	140	107	183	72	218	35	255	2465	
19	271	95	195	170	120	137	156	142	152	138	165	125	65	225	12	278	2465	
277	13	96	194	129	161	139	151	145	133	157	127	163	217	73	29	261	2465	
287	3	87	203	181	109	149	141	144	136	155	106	184	186	104	231	59	2465	
268	22	82	208	132	158	147	143	146	154	135	171	119	187	103	275	15	2465	
248	42	216	74	105	185	115	176	118	112	159	173	162	214	76	281	9	2465	
34	256	86	204	124	166	175	114	172	178	131	117	128	211	79	237	53	2465	
47	243	228	62	192	70	69	77	196	201	212	64	219	85	210	233	57	2465	
40	250	227	63	98	220	221	213	94	89	78	226	71	205	80	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465																		

7	mgc	2374	2330	2437	2215	3164	1825	2769	2510	3213	1881	2919	2381	1867	2558	2352	2645	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	200	75	102	191	193	81	199	202	67	61	224	92	198	21	269	2465	
18	272	90	215	188	99	97	209	91	88	223	229	66	93	197	232	58	2465	
273	17	206	84	110	121	177	167	164	168	108	179	111	190	100	239	51	2465	
43	247	83	207	180	169	113	123	126	122	182	160	130	68	222	24	266	2465	
33	257	189	101	174	116	154	157	137	139	138	107	183	72	218	35	255	2465	
19	271	95	195	170	120	134	144	149	142	156	165	125	65	225	12	278	2465	
277	13	96	194	129	161	150	143	145	147	140	127	163	217	73	29	261	2465	
287	3	87	203	181	109	135	148	141	146	155	106	184	186	104	231	59	2465	
268	22	82	208	132	158	152	133	153	151	136	171	119	187	103	275	15	2465	
248	42	216	74	105	185	115	176	118	112	159	173	162	214	76	281	9	2465	
34	256	86	204	124	166	175	114	172	178	131	117	128	211	79	237	53	2465	
47	243	228	62	192	70	69	77	196	201	212	64	219	85	210	233	57	2465	
40	250	227	63	98	220	221	213	94	89	78	226	71	205	80	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465																		

8	mgc	2372	2445	2523	2174	2806	2108	2621	2717	2953	2333	2466	2384	2116	2383	2438	2601	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	218	206	208	210	212	214	71	70	68	66	64	62	216	21	269	2465	
18	272	81	96	104	102	100	98	197	198	200	202	204	94	209	232	58	2465	
273	17	83	203	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	87	207	239	51	2465	
43	247	79	205	105	162	158	160	125	124	122	164	185	85	211	24	266	2465	
33	257	77	201	107	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	183	89	213	35	255	2465	
19	271	75	199	109	123	134	144	149	142	156	167	181	91	215	12	278	2465	
277	13	73	95	177	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	113	195	217	29	261	2465	
287	3	221	97	175	161	135	148	141	146	155	129	115	193	69	231	59	2465	
268	22	223	99	173	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	117	191	67	275	15	2465	
248	42	225	101	171	126	132	130	165	166	168	128	119	189	65	281	9	2465	
34	256	227	103	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	187	63	237	53	2465	
47	243	229	196	186	188	190	192	93	92	90	88	86	194	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	74	84	82	80	78	76	219	220	222	224	226	228	72	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465 2465																		

9	mgc	2494	2147	2523	2250	3051	1843	2756	2546	3234	1880	2834	2437	1874	2489	2407	2675	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	200	75	102	191	193	81	199	202	67	61	224	92	198	21	269	2465	
18	272	90	215	188	99	97	209	91	88	223	229	66	93	197	232	58	2465	
273	17	206	84	131	168	136	144	112	179	124	173	138	190	100	239	51	2465	
43	247	83	207	132	127	176	184	143	108	137	129	169	68	222	24	266	2465	
33	257	189	101	172	140	123	107	180	148	174	133	128	72	218	35	255	2465	
19	271	95	195	162	157	116	149	105	181	142	110	183	65	225	12	278	2465	
277	13	96	194	121	161	153	177	145	113	182	147	106	217	73	29	261	2465	
287	3	87	203	152	117	166	109	185	141	111	178	146	186	104	231	59	2465	
268	22	82	208	126	175	134	167	150	118	160	155	120	187	103	275	15	2465	
248	42	216	74	139	125	171	114	163	158	119	165	151	214	76	281	9	2465	
34	256	86	204	170	135	130	154	122	159	156	115	164	211	79	237	53	2465	
47	243	228	62	192	70	69	77	196	201	212	64	219	85	210	233	57	2465	
40	250	227	63	98	220	221	213	94	89	78	226	71	205	80	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

10	mgc	2448	2219	2536	2181	3060	1819	2779	2560	3215	1869	2850	2383	1970	2501	2457	2593	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	200	75	102	191	193	81	199	202	67	61	224	92	198	21	269	2465	
18	272	90	215	188	99	97	209	91	88	223	229	66	93	197	232	58	2465	
273	17	206	84	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	190	100	239	51	2465	
43	247	83	207	105	162	158	160	125	124	122	164	185	68	222	24	266	2465	
33	257	189	101	107	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	183	72	218	35	255	2465	
19	271	95	195	109	123	134	144	149	142	156	167	181	65	225	12	278	2465	
277	13	96	194	177	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	113	217	73	29	261	2465	
287	3	87	203	175	161	135	148	141	146	155	129	115	186	104	231	59	2465	
268	22	82	208	173	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	117	187	103	275	15	2465	
248	42	216	74	171	126	132	130	165	166	168	128	119	214	76	281	9	2465	
34	256	86	204	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	211	79	237	53	2465	
47	243	228	62	192	70	69	77	196	201	212	64	219	85	210	233	57	2465	
40	250	227	63	98	220	221	213	94	89	78	226	71	205	80	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

11	mgc	2356	2460	2582	2179	2783	1982	2679	2490	3273	2040	2590	2610	2042	2159	2432	2783	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	142	149	144	157	133	159	131	176	114	99	191	84	206	21	269	2465	
18	272	147	145	143	156	134	165	125	174	116	96	194	73	217	232	58	2465	
273	17	146	141	148	136	154	126	164	111	179	199	91	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	140	138	155	139	153	121	169	110	180	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	150	152	135	137	151	124	166	172	118	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	122	123	163	160	161	158	128	170	120	94	196	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	168	167	127	130	129	162	132	178	112	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	181	185	119	115	113	183	117	108	184	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	109	105	171	175	177	107	173	106	182	103	187	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

12	mgc	2356	2460	2582	2179	2774	1975	2687	2494	3273	2055	2598	2602	2031	2159	2432	2783	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	133	139	145	151	157	159	131	176	114	99	191	84	206	21	269	2465	
18	272	150	156	137	138	144	165	125	174	116	96	194	73	217	232	58	2465	
273	17	142	143	149	155	136	126	164	111	179	199	91	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	154	135	141	147	148	121	169	110	180	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	146	152	153	134	140	124	166	172	118	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	122	123	163	160	161	158	128	170	120	94	196	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	168	167	127	130	129	162	132	178	112	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	181	185	119	115	113	183	117	108	184	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	109	105	171	175	177	107	173	106	182	103	187	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

13	mgc	2356	2460	2582	2179	2795	1977	2675	2475	3273	2040	2601	2626	2027	2159	2432	2783	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	154	157	137	139	138	159	131	176	114	99	191	84	206	21	269	2465	
18	272	134	144	149	142	156	165	125	174	116	96	194	73	217	232	58	2465	
273	17	150	143	145	147	140	126	164	111	179	199	91	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	135	148	141	146	155	121	169	110	180	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	152	133	153	151	136	124	166	172	118	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	122	123	163	160	161	158	128	170	120	94	196	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	168	167	127	130	129	162	132	178	112	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	181	185	119	115	113	183	117	108	184	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	109	105	171	175	177	107	173	106	182	103	187	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

14	mgc	2356	2460	2584	2177	2762	1975	2692	2465	3294	2067	2590	2633	2045	2142	2438	2760	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	121	129	137	145	153	161	169	176	114	99	191	82	208	21	269	2465	
18	272	160	168	127	128	136	144	152	174	116	96	194	73	217	232	58	2465	
273	17	143	151	159	167	126	134	135	111	179	199	91	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	133	141	142	150	158	166	125	110	180	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	165	124	132	140	148	149	157	172	118	95	195	84	206	35	255	2465	
19	271	155	156	164	123	131	139	147	170	120	94	196	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	138	146	154	162	163	122	130	178	112	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	181	185	119	115	113	183	117	108	184	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	109	105	171	175	177	107	173	106	182	103	187	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

15	mgc	2352	2460	2582	2179	2803	1965	2715	2492	3226	2029	2590	2617	2017	2173	2448	2792	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	162	158	160	125	124	122	164	176	114	99	191	84	206	21	269	2465	
18	272	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	174	116	96	194	77	213	232	58	2465	
273	17	161	134	144	149	142	156	129	111	179	199	91	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	110	180	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	123	135	148	141	146	155	167	172	118	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	170	120	94	196	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	126	132	130	165	166	168	128	178	112	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	181	185	119	115	113	183	117	108	184	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	109	105	171	175	177	107	173	106	182	103	187	73	217	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

16	mgc	2482	2613	2454	2160	2864	1903	2673	2490	3274	2046	2632	2505	2042	2267	2440	2595	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	126	175	134	131	168	136	142	110	183	99	191	73	217	21	269	2465	
18	272	139	125	171	132	127	176	182	147	106	96	194	84	206	232	58	2465	
273	17	170	135	130	172	140	123	111	178	146	94	196	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	144	112	179	149	105	181	124	173	138	103	187	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	184	143	108	177	145	113	137	129	169	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	107	180	148	109	185	141	174	133	128	199	91	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	162	157	116	167	150	118	160	155	120	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	121	161	153	114	163	158	119	165	151	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	152	117	166	154	122	159	156	115	164	200	90	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	101	92	201	197	104	202	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	189	198	89	93	186	88	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

17	mgc	2411	2589	2476	2175	2753	1975	2695	2477	3341	2052	2582	2520	2042	2293	2429	2630	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	99	191	73	217	21	269	2465	
18	272	105	162	158	160	125	124	122	164	185	94	196	84	206	232	58	2465	
273	17	107	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	183	96	194	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	109	123	134	144	149	142	156	167	181	200	90	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	177	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	113	95	195	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	175	161	135	148	141	146	155	129	115	199	91	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	173	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	117	203	87	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	171	126	132	130	165	166	168	128	119	204	86	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	103	187	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	102	92	101	202	197	104	201	98	100	205	193	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	188	198	189	88	93	186	89	192	190	97	85	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

18	mgc	2521	2483	2382	2221	2826	1766	2542	2608	3296	2042	2627	2551	2185	2368	2432	2590	2465
267	46	4	25	2	32	236	259	262	279	242	263	1	252	5	37	253	2465	
23	244	286	265	288	258	54	31	28	11	48	27	289	38	285	7	283	2465	
50	240	96	104	102	100	98	197	198	200	202	204	94	73	217	21	269	2465	
18	272	205	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	85	84	206	232	58	2465	
273	17	101	105	162	158	124	125	160	122	164	185	189	72	218	239	51	2465	
43	247	201	107	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	183	89	216	74	24	266	2465	
33	257	199	109	123	134	144	149	142	156	167	181	91	82	208	35	255	2465	
19	271	95	177	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	113	195	223	67	12	278	2465	
277	13	97	175	161	135	148	141	146	155	129	115	193	227	63	29	261	2465	
287	3	99	173	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	117	191	222	68	231	59	2465	
268	22	203	171	126	132	166	165	130	168	128	119	87	77	213	275	15	2465	
248	42	103	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	187	83	207	281	9	2465	
34	256	196	186	188	190	192	93	92	90	88	86	194	228	62	237	53	2465	
47	243	212	66	214	215	211	64	219	65	209	70	210	69	61	233	57	2465	
40	250	78	224	76	75	79	226	71	225	81	220	80	229	221	282	8	2465	
254	36	60	56	235	246	264	10	14	20	238	16	241	245	249	30	251	2465	
284	6	230	234	55	44	26	280	276	270	52	274	49	45	41	260	39	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

19	mgc	2247	2172	2757	3139	1880	2579	2216	2374	2398	2640	2717	2338	2706	2072	2465	2740	2465
146	147	142	157	133	132	158	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
141	145	149	156	134	125	165	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
148	143	144	136	154	128	162	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
150	152	135	137	151	169	121	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465	
140	138	155	139	153	167	123	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
126	122	161	124	160	163	159	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
164	168	129	166	130	131	127	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465	
179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

20	mgc	2254	2155	2765	3132	1880	2594	2209	2393	2380	2640	2717	2338	2706	2072	2465	2740	2465
153	134	148	150	140	132	158	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
137	156	142	152	138	125	165	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
139	151	145	133	157	128	162	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
149	141	144	136	155	169	121	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465	
147	143	146	154	135	167	123	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
126	122	161	124	160	163	159	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
164	168	129	166	130	131	127	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465	
179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

21	mgc	2255	2175	2753	3106	1880	2613	2209	2390	2381	2640	2717	2338	2706	2072	2465	2740	2465
154	157	137	139	138	132	158	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
134	144	149	142	156	125	165	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
150	143	145	147	140	128	162	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
135	148	141	146	155	169	121	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465	
152	133	153	151	136	167	123	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
126	122	161	124	160	163	159	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
164	168	129	166	130	131	127	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465	
179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

22	mgc	2222	2173	2770	3096	1901	2663	2216	2356	2387	2593	2760	2317	2709	2072	2465	2740	2465
121	129	137	145	153	161	169	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
160	168	127	128	136	144	152	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
143	151	159	167	126	134	135	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
133	141	142	150	158	166	125	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465	
165	124	132	140	148	149	157	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
155	156	164	123	131	139	147	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
138	146	154	162	163	122	130	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465	
179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

23	mgc	2263	2163	2759	3119	1871	2625	2216	2340	2397	2624	2732	2347	2707	2072	2465	2740	2465
162	158	160	125	124	122	164	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
121	154	157	137	139	138	169	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
123	134	144	149	142	156	167	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
163	150	143	145	147	140	127	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465	
161	135	148	141	146	155	129	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
159	152	133	153	151	136	131	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
126	132	130	165	166	168	128	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465	
179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

24	mgc	2164	2184	2771	3155	1845	2636	2158	2384	2398	2656	2645	2370	2621	2183	2438	2832	2465
131	168	136	144	112	179	124	173	138	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
132	127	176	184	143	108	137	129	169	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
172	140	123	107	180	148	174	133	128	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
162	157	116	149	105	181	142	110	183	101	189	212	78	41	249	2	288	2465	
121	161	153	177	145	113	182	147	106	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
152	117	166	109	185	141	111	178	146	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
126	175	134	167	150	118	160	155	120	205	85	211	79	54	236	5	285	2465	
139	125	171	114	163	158	119	165	151	93	197	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
170	135	130	154	122	159	156	115	164	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	96	200	100	98	102	204	193	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	194	90	190	192	188	86	97	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	208	67	213	209	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	82	223	77	81	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	277	24	17	18	284	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	13	266	273	272	6	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

25	mgc	2224	2185	2855	3093	1838	2701	2107	2387	2398	2502	2932	2175	2703	2192	2420	2728	2465
110	121	177	167	164	168	108	179	111	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
180	169	113	123	126	122	182	160	130	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
174	116	146	147	142	157	133	107	183	99	191	210	80	253	37	4	286	2465	
170	120	141	145	149	156	134	165	125	205	85	212	78	41	249	2	288	2465	
129	161	148	143	144	136	154	127	163	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
181	109	150	152	135	137	151	106	184	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
132	158	140	138	155	139	153	171	119	93	197	211	79	54	236	5	285	2465	
105	185	115	176	118	112	159	173	162	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
124	166	175	114	172	178	131	117	128	95	195	68	222	254	36	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

26	mgc	2224	2185	2855	3093	1845	2684	2115	2380	2398	2517	2925	2194	2685	2192	2420	2728	2465
110	121	177	167	164	168	108	179	111	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
180	169	113	123	126	122	182	160	130	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
174	116	153	134	148	150	140	107	183	99	191	210	80	253	37	4	286	2465	
170	120	137	156	142	152	138	165	125	205	85	212	78	41	249	2	288	2465	
129	161	139	151	145	133	157	127	163	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
181	109	149	141	144	136	155	106	184	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
132	158	147	143	146	154	135	171	119	93	197	211	79	54	236	5	285	2465	
105	185	115	176	118	112	159	173	162	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
124	166	175	114	172	178	131	117	128	95	195	68	222	254	36	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

27	mgc	2224	2185	2855	3093	1846	2704	2103	2354	2398	2536	2925	2191	2686	2192	2420	2728	2465
110	121	177	167	164	168	108	179	111	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
180	169	113	123	126	122	182	160	130	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
174	116	154	157	137	139	138	107	183	99	191	210	80	253	37	4	286	2465	
170	120	134	144	149	142	156	165	125	205	85	212	78	41	249	2	288	2465	
129	161	150	143	145	147	140	127	163	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465	
181	109	135	148	141	146	155	106	184	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465	
132	158	152	133	153	151	136	171	119	93	197	211	79	54	236	5	285	2465	
105	185	115	176	118	112	159	173	162	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
124	166	175	114	172	178	131	117	128	95	195	68	222	254	36	263	27	2465	
103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

28	mgc	2275	2173	2786	3112	2069	2510	2208	2302	2398	2610	2814	2184	2758	2088	2414	2739	2465
112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465	
105	162	158	160	125	124	122	164	185	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465	
107	121	154	157	137	139	138	169	183	101	189	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465	
109	123	134	144	149	142	156	167	181	205	85	212	78	41	249	2	288	2465	
177	163	150	143	145	147	140	127	113	201	89	63	227	255	35	270	20	2465	
175	161	135	148	141	146	155	129	115	202	88	69	221	57	233	267	23	2465	
173	159	152	133	153	151	136	131	117	99	191	211	79	54	236	5	285	2465	
171	126	132	130	165	166	168	128	119	93	197	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465	
176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465	
103	193	96	100	98	102	200	204	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465	
187	97	194	190	192	188	90	86	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465	
206	66	64	218	61	71	67	213	208	220	209	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465	
84	224	226	72	229	219	223	77	82	70	81	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465	
239	42	40	231	232	44	234	241	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465	
51	248	250	59	58	246	56	49	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465	
289	277	24	17	18	284	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465	
1	13	266	273	272	6	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465	
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 136 and 119

Let's consider **bordered** magic square of orders 7 and 8 given by

7x7								175
	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
	1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
	3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
	43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
	41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
	39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

8x8									260
	8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
	5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60	260
	6	16	31	36	25	38	49	59	260
	11	22	26	37	32	35	43	54	260
	61	24	40	27	34	29	41	4	260
	56	42	33	30	39	28	23	9	260
	55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10	260
	58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

The entries of above two magic squares are sequential numbers starting from 1:

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{1, 2, \dots, 63, 64\}$$

The property of **bordered** magic squares is that removing the upper borders still we are left with magic squares of sequential values.

Multiplying each entry of above two magic squares of orders 7 and 8 by 289, we get

7x7								50575
	12138	10982	11560	1445	1156	578	12716	50575
	289	9826	10693	4913	5491	5202	14161	50575
	867	4046	6936	8381	6358	10404	13583	50575
	12427	4335	6647	7225	7803	10115	2023	50575
	11849	8670	8092	6069	7514	5780	2601	50575
	11271	9248	3757	9537	8959	4624	3179	50575
	1734	3468	2890	13005	13294	13872	2312	50575
	50575	50575	50575	50575	50575	50575	50575	50575

8x8									75140
	2312	578	17918	18496	14739	3757	15317	2023	75140
	1445	13294	12716	4913	14450	5202	5780	17340	75140
	1734	4624	8959	10404	7225	10982	14161	17051	75140
	3179	6358	7514	10693	9248	10115	12427	15606	75140
	17629	6936	11560	7803	9826	8381	11849	1156	75140
	16184	12138	9537	8670	11271	8092	6647	2601	75140
	15895	13005	6069	13872	4335	13583	5491	2890	75140
	16762	18207	867	289	4046	15028	3468	16473	75140
	75140	75140	75140	75140	75140	75140	75140	75140	75140

In this case, the entries distributions of these two magic squares are given by

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{289, 578, \dots, 13672, 14161\}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{289, 578, \dots, 8207, 18496\}$$

Let's replace entries of above two magic squares by magic squares of order 17. In each case, the entries chosen are as given below:

$$289 \rightarrow 1, 2, \dots, 289$$

$$578 \rightarrow 290, 291, \dots, 578$$

$$867 \rightarrow 579, 580, \dots, 867$$

$$\dots \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

$$\dots \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

This lead us to two big **bordered** magic squares of orders 136 and 119 multiples of 17. Since these two magic squares

are very big, these are given in **excel files** attached with this work. There are total 28 magic squares of orders 136 and 119 multiples of order 17.

The multiples blocks are with 28 different kinds of magic squares of order 17. Based on these two big magic squares we get the following magic squares.

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 51

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 51 obtained from magic squares of order 119. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{119^2 - 51^2}{2} := 5780$ from each entry of magic square order 119, we get the following three magic squares of order 51:

4	mgc	65991	64740	64353	63705	63048	61962	60840	60423	57540	57117	56019	54915	54264	53592	53211	51984	51612	53853	55203	57417	59370	61314	62829	64308	66492	66210	68388	69891	71388	73338	75267	77487	78861	81090	80730	79479	79092	78444	77787	76701	75879	75162	72279	71856	70758	69654	69003	68331	67950	66723	66351
1141	869	871	873	875	877	879	881	882	1137	1135	1133	1131	1129	1127	1125	1139	2586	2314	2316	2318	2320	2322	2324	2326	2327	2582	2580	2578	2576	2574	2572	2570	2584	563	291	293	295	297	299	301	303	304	559	557	555	553	551	549	547	561	66351	
1156	1028	1025	1045	1043	1044	903	900	920	918	919	1078	1075	1095	1093	1094	868	2601	2473	2470	2490	2488	2489	2348	2345	2365	2363	2364	2523	2520	2540	2538	2539	2313	578	450	447	467	465	466	325	322	342	340	341	500	497	517	515	516	290	66351	
1154	1048	1038	1033	1040	1026	923	913	908	915	901	1098	1088	1083	1090	1076	870	2599	2493	2483	2478	2485	2471	2368	2358	2353	2360	2346	2543	2533	2528	2535	2521	2315	576	470	460	455	462	448	345	335	330	337	323	520	510	505	512	498	292	66351	
1152	1047	1039	1037	1035	1027	922	914	912	910	902	1097	1089	1087	1085	1077	872	2597	2492	2484	2482	2480	2472	2367	2359	2357	2355	2347	2542	2534	2532	2530	2522	2317	574	469	461	459	457	449	344	336	334	332	324	519	511	509	507	499	294	66351	
1150	1032	1034	1041	1036	1042	907	909	916	911	917	1082	1084	1091	1086	1092	874	2595	2477	2479	2486	2481	2487	2352	2354	2361	2356	2362	2527	2529	2536	2531	2537	2319	572	454	456	463	458	464	329	331	338	333	339	504	506	513	508	514	296	66351	
1148	1030	1049	1029	1031	1046	905	924	904	906	921	1080	1099	1079	1081	1096	876	2593	2475	2494	2474	2476	2491	2350	2369	2349	2351	2366	2525	2544	2524	2526	2541	2321	570	452	471	451	453	468	327	346	326	328	343	502	521	501	503	518	298	66351	
1146	1053	1050	1070	1068	1069	1003	1000	1020	1018	1019	953	950	970	968	969	878	2591	2498	2495	2515	2513	2514	2448	2445	2465	2463	2464	2398	2395	2415	2413	2414	2323	568	475	472	492	490	491	425	422	442	440	441	375	372	392	390	391	300	66351	
1144	1073	1063	1058	1065	1051	1023	1013	1008	1015	1001	973	963	958	965	951	880	2589	2518	2508	2503	2510	2496	2468	2458	2453	2460	2446	2418	2408	2403	2410	2396	2325	566	495	485	480	487	473	445	435	430	437	423	395	385	380	387	373	302	66351	
884	1072	1064	1062	1060	1052	1022	1014	1012	1010	1002	972	964	962	960	952	1140	2329	2517	2509	2507	2505	2497	2467	2459	2457	2455	2447	2417	2409	2407	2405	2397	2585	306	494	486	484	482	474	444	436	434	432	424	394	386	384	382	374	562	66351	
886	1057	1059	1066	1061	1067	1007	1009	1016	1011	1017	957	959	966	961	967	1138	2331	2502	2504	2511	2506	2512	2452	2454	2461	2456	2462	2402	2404	2411	2406	2412	2583	308	479	481	488	483	489	429	431	438	433	439	379	381	388	383	389	560	66351	
888	1055	1074	1054	1056	1071	1005	1024	1004	1006	1021	955	974	954	956	971	1136	2333	2500	2519	2499	2501	2516	2450	2469	2449	2451	2466	2400	2419	2399	2401	2416	2581	310	477	496	476	478	493	427	446	426	428	443	377	396	376	378	393	558	66351	
890	928	925	945	943	944	1103	1100	1120	1118	1119	978	975	995	993	994	1134	2335	2373	2370	2390	2388	2389	2548	2545	2565	2563	2564	2423	2420	2440	2438	2439	2579	312	350	347	367	365	366	525	522	542	540	541	400	397	417	415	416	556	66351	
892	948	938	933	940	926	1123	1113	1108	1115	1101	998	988	983	990	976	1132	2337	2393	2383	2378	2385	2371	2568	2558	2553	2560	2566	2443	2433	2428	2435	2421	2577	314	370	360	355	362	348	545	535	530	537	523	420	410	405	412	398	554	66351	
894	947	939	937	935	927	1122	1114	1112	1110	1102	997	989	987	985	977	1130	2339	2392	2384	2382	2380	2372	2567	2559	2557	2555	2547	2442	2434	2432	2430	2422	2575	316	369	361	359	357	349	544	536	534	532	524	419	411	409	407	399	552	66351	
896	932	934	941	936	942	1107	1109	1116	1111	1117	982	984	991	986	992	1128	2341	2377	2379	2386	2381	2387	2552	2554	2561	2556	2562	2427	2429	2436	2431	2437	2573	318	354	356	363	358	364	529	531	538	533	539	404	406	413	408	414	550	66351	
898	930	949	929	931	946	1105	1124	1104	1106	1121	980	999	979	981	996	1126	2343	2375	2394	2374	2376	2391	2550	2569	2549	2551	2566	2425	2444	2424	2426	2441	2571	320	352	371	351	353	368	527	546	526	528	543	402	421	401	403	418	548	66351	
885	1155	1153	1151	1149	1147	1145	1143	1142	887	889	891	893	895	897	899	883	2330	2600	2598	2596	2594	2592	2590	2588	2587	2332	2334	2336	2338	2340	2342	2344	2328	307	577	575	573	571	569	567	565	564	309	311	313	315	317	319	321	305	66351	
852	580	582	584	586	588	590	592	593	848	846	844	842	840	838	836	850	1430	1158	1160	1162	1164	1166	1168	1170	1171	1426	1424	1422	1420	1418	1416	1414	1428	2008	1736	1738	1740	1742	1744	1746	1748	1749	2004	2002	2000	1998	1996	1994	1992	2006	66351	
867	739	736	756	754	755	614	611	631	629	630	789	786	806	804	805	579	1445	1317	1314	1334	1332	1333	1192	1189	1209	1207	1208	1367	1364	1384	1382	1383	1157	2023	1895	1892	1912	1910	1911	1770	1767	1787	1785	1786	1945	1942	1962	1960	1961	1735	66351	
865	759	749	744	751	737	634	624	619	626	612	809	799	794	801	787	581	1443	1337	1327	1322	1329	1315	1212	1202	1197	1204	1190	1387	1377	1372	1379	1365	1159	2021	1915	1905	1900	1907	1893	1790	1780	1775	1782	1768	1965	1955	1950	1957	1943	1737	66351	
863	758	750	748	746	738	633	625	623	621	613	808	800	798	796	788	583	1441	1336	1328	1326	1324	1316	1211	1203	1201	1199	1191	1386	1378	1376	1374	1366	1161	2019	1914	1906	1904	1902	1894	1789	1781	1779	1777	1769	1964	1956	1954	1952	1944	1739	66351	
861	743	745	752	747	753	618	620	627	622	628	793	795	802	797	803	585	1439	1321	1323	1330	1325	1331	1196	1198	1205	1200	1206	1371	1373	1380	1375	1381	1163	2017	1899	1901	1908	1903	1909	1774	1776	1783	1778	1784	1949	1951	1958	1953	1959	1741	66351	
859	741	760	740	742	757	616	635	615	617	632	791	810	790	792	807	587	1437	1319	1338	1318	1320	1335	1194	1213	1193	1195	1210	1369	1388	1368	1370	1385	1165	2015	1897	1916	1896	1898	1913	1772	1791	1771	1773	1788	1947	1966	1946	1948	1963	1743	66351	
857	764	761	781	779	780	714	711	731	729	730	664	661	681	679	680	589	1435	1342	1339	1359	1357	1358	1292	1289	1309	1307	1308	1242	1239	1259	1257	1258	1167	2013	1920	1917	1937	1935	1936	1870	1867	1887	1885	1886	1820	1817	1837	1835	1836	1745	66351	
855	784	774	769	776	762	734	724	719	726	712	684	674	669	676	662	591	1433	1362	1352	1347	1354	1340	1312	1302	1297	1304	1290	1262	1252	1247	1254	1240	1169	2011	1940	1930	1925	1932	1918	1890	1880	1875	1882	1868	1840	1830	1825	1832	1818	1747	66351	
595	783	775	773	771	763	733	725	723	721	713	683	675	673	671	663	851	1173	1361	1353	1351	1349	1341	1311	1303	1301	1299																										

10	mgc	65811	64832	63999	63741	61062	62598	59640	59340	56124	58956	56439	55812	56349	55131	53445	51925	51612	53673	55095	56463	59406	59328	63465	63108	65409	64794	70227	70311	71985	75423	76806	77721	78402	81090	80550	79371	78138	78480	75801	77337	74379	74079	70863	73695	71178	70251	71088	69870	68184	66264	66351
890	1111	1153	1132	1155	1125	921	898	895	878	915	894	1156	905	1152	1120	904	2335	2556	2598	2577	2600	2570	2366	2343	2340	2323	2360	2339	2601	2350	2597	2565	2349	312	533	575	554	577	547	343	320	317	300	337	316	578	327	574	542	326	66351	
1134	913	871	892	869	899	1103	1126	1129	1146	1109	1130	868	1119	872	1150	874	2579	2358	2316	2337	2314	2344	2548	2571	2574	2591	2554	2575	2313	2564	2317	2595	2319	556	335	293	314	291	321	525	548	551	568	531	552	290	541	294	572	296	66351	
1107	917	1015	1008	1013	1000	1024	998	1026	981	1043	1058	966	1073	951	1136	888	2552	2362	2460	2453	2458	2445	2469	2443	2471	2426	2488	2503	2411	2518	2396	2581	2333	529	339	437	430	435	422	446	420	448	403	465	480	388	495	373	558	310	66351	
1139	885	1010	1012	1014	1001	1023	992	1032	983	1041	1061	963	1084	940	925	1099	2584	2330	2455	2457	2459	2446	2468	2437	2477	2428	2486	2506	2408	2529	2385	2370	2544	561	307	432	434	436	423	445	414	454	405	463	483	385	506	362	347	521	66351	
884	1140	1011	1016	1009	1021	1003	1031	993	1046	978	958	1066	1085	939	918	1106	2329	2585	2456	2461	2454	2466	2448	2476	2438	2491	2423	2403	2511	2530	2384	2363	2551	306	562	433	438	431	443	425	453	415	468	400	380	488	507	361	340	528	66351	
1114	910	1007	1019	1002	1018	1004	1036	988	1047	977	957	1067	941	1083	1133	891	2559	2355	2462	2464	2447	2463	2449	2481	2433	2492	2422	2402	2512	2386	2528	2578	2336	536	332	439	441	424	440	426	458	410	469	399	379	489	363	505	555	313	66351	
1124	900	1007	1005	1022	1020	1006	1033	991	985	1039	1062	962	1075	949	925	1092	2569	2345	2452	2450	2467	2465	2451	2478	2436	2430	2484	2504	2407	2520	2394	2567	2347	546	322	429	427	444	442	428	455	413	407	461	484	384	497	371	544	324	66351	
1138	886	1035	1034	994	997	996	999	1029	987	1037	1063	961	934	1090	1145	879	2583	2331	2480	2479	2439	2442	2441	2444	2474	2432	2482	2508	2406	2379	2535	2590	2324	560	308	457	456	416	419	418	421	451	409	459	485	383	356	512	567	301	66351	
880	1144	989	990	1030	1027	1028	995	1025	979	1045	954	1070	930	1094	1128	896	2325	2589	2434	2435	2475	2472	2473	2440	2470	2424	2490	2399	2515	2375	2539	2573	2341	302	566	411	412	452	449	450	417	447	401	467	376	492	352	516	550	318	66351	
870	1154	976	972	1038	1042	1044	974	1040	1049	973	953	1071	935	1089	926	1098	2315	2599	2421	2417	2483	2487	2489	2419	2485	2494	2418	2398	2516	2230	2534	2371	2543	292	576	398	394	460	464	466	396	462	471	395	375	493	357	511	348	520	66351	
889	1135	1048	1052	986	982	980	1050	984	1051	975	1054	970	1080	944	882	1142	2334	2580	2493	2497	2431	2427	2425	2495	2429	2496	2420	2499	2415	2525	2389	2327	2587	311	557	470	474	408	404	402	472	406	473	397	476	392	502	366	304	564	66351	
909	1111	1055	1065	1056	955	960	1053	956	1059	1057	952	964	1074	950	876	1148	2354	2560	2500	2510	2501	2400	2405	2498	2401	2504	2502	2397	2409	2519	2595	2321	2593	331	537	477	487	478	377	382	475	378	481	479	374	386	496	372	298	570	66351	
1123	901	969	959	968	1069	1064	971	1068	965	967	1060	1072	929	1095	920	1104	2568	2346	2414	2404	2413	2410	2509	2416	2513	2410	2412	2505	2517	2334	2540	2365	2549	545	323	397	381	390	491	486	393	490	387	389	482	354	517	342	526	66351		
1110	914	945	1091	943	942	946	1093	938	1092	948	1087	947	1088	1096	924	1100	2555	2359	2390	2536	2388	2387	2391	2538	2383	2537	2393	2532	2392	2533	2541	2369	2545	532	336	367	513	365	364	368	515	360	514	370	509	369	510	518	346	522	66351	
1117	907	1079	993	1081	1082	1077	931	1086	932	1076	937	1077	928	936	875	1149	2562	2352	2524	2378	2526	2527	2523	2376	2531	2377	2521	2382	2522	2373	2381	2320	2594	539	329	501	355	503	504	500	353	508	354	498	359	499	350	358	297	571	66351	
903	1121	1097	911	922	911	893	1147	1143	1137	919	1141	916	912	908	1127	906	2348	2566	2542	2546	2367	2356	2338	2592	2588	2582	2364	2586	2361	2357	2353	2572	2351	325	543	519	523	344	333	315	569	565	559	341	563	338	334	330	549	528	66351	
873	1151	927	923	1102	1113	1131	877	881	887	1105	883	1108	1112	1116	897	1118	2318	2596	2372	2368	2547	2558	2576	2322	2326	2332	2550	2328	2553	2557	2561	2342	2563	295	573	349	345	524	535	553	299	303	309	527	305	530	534	538	319	540	66351	
601	822	864	843	866	836	632	609	606	589	626	605	867	616	863	831	615	1179	1400	1442	1421	1444	1414	1210	1187	1184	1167	1204	1183	1445	1194	1441	1409	1193	1757	1978	2020	1999	2022	1992	1788	1765	1762	1745	1782	1761	2023	1772	2019	1987	1771	66351	
845	624	582	603	580	610	814	837	840	857	820	841	579	830	583	861	585	1423	1202	1160	1181	1158	1188	1392	1415	1418	1365	1398	1419	1157	1408	1161	1439	1163	2001	1780	1738	1759	1736	1766	1970	1993	1996	2013	1976	1969	1735	1986	1739	2017	1741	66351	
818	628	726	719	724	711	735	709	737	692	754	769	677	784	662	847	599	1396	1206	1304	1297	1302	1289	1313	1287	1315	1270	1332	1347	1255	1362	1240	1425	1177	1974	1784	1882	1875	1880	1867	1891	1865	1893	1848	1910	1925	1833	1940	1818	2003	1755	66351	
850	596	721	723	725	712	734	703	743	694	752	772	674	795	651	636	810	1428	1174	1299	1301	1303	1290	1312	1281	1321	1272	1330	1350	1252	1373	1229	1214	1388	2006	1752	1877	1879	1881	1868	1890	1859	1899	1850	1908	1928	1830	1951	1807	1792	1966	66351	
595	851	722	727	720	732	714	742	704	757	689	669	777	796	650	629	817	1173	1429	1300	1305	1298	1310	1292	1320	1282	1335	1267	1247	1355	1374	1228	1207	1395	1751	2007	1878	1883	1876	1888	1870	1898	1860	1913	1845	1825	1933	1952	1806	1785	1973	66351	
825	621	728	730	713	729	715	747	699	758	688	668	778	652	794	844	602	1403	1199	1306	1308	1291	1307	1293	1325	1277	1336	1266	1246	1356	1230	1372	1422	1180	1981	1777	1884	1886	1869	1885													

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers - <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>.
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares - <https://numbers-magic.com/?cat=3>.

References

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [1] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>
- [2] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.

[8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

• Bordered Magic Squares

[9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.

[10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.

[11] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.

[12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.

[13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.

[14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.

[15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>

• Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21, 21^2 and 2021. **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-118, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares

- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.

- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Magic and Bordered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, September 10, pp. 1-99 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500134>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 8, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-80, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514396>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 10, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514398>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12, **Zenodo**, September 23, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5523608>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 14, **Zenodo**, September 26, pp. 1-198, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528867>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 3, **Zenodo**, May 05, pp. 1-29, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898383>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 5, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8175759>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 7, **Zenodo**, July 23, pp. 1-34, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176061>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 9, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2023, pp. 1-28, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176357>.
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 11, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-34, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176475>.

[34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 13, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-32, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178879>.

[35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 15, **Zenodo**, July 24, pp. 1-35, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178935>.

[36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 17, **Zenodo**, July 25, pp. 1-26, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8180965>.

• Magic Squares With Bordered Magic Rectangles

[37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319985>.

[38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 14 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319787>.

[39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-63, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320116>.

[40] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320131>.

[41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320877>.

[42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 6 to 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225854>.

- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 20 to 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-100, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225886>.
- [44] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 24, 2023, pp. 1-76, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565946>
- [45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 30, 2023, pp. 1-102, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7585787>
- [46] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 42 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-92, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695834>.
- [47] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-69, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695939>
- [48] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696070>.
- [49] **Inder J. Taneja**, Closed Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-28, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696181>.
- [50] **Inder J. Taneja**, 8000+ Magic Squares of Order 22 in Different Styles, Models and Designs, **Zenodo**, April 08, pp. 1-135, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809478>.

• Figured Magic Squares and Bordered Magic Rectangles

- [51] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 6, 10, 12, 14 and 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377674>.

- [52] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 18 and 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-87, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377689>.
- [53] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 22 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-61, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377706>.
- [54] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 24 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-104, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377779>.
- [55] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 26 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377794>.
- [56] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 28 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390666>.
- [57] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390705>.
- [58] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 32 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2022, pp. 1-310, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472891>.
- [59] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 34 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-193, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486540>.
- [60] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 36 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-140, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486548>.
- [61] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 38 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-133, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7500188>.

[62] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 40 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-157, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7500192>.

• Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares

[63] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.

[64] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.

[65] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.

[66] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.

[67] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.

[68] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.

• Odd Order Magic Squares

[69] **Inder J. Taneja**, Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043030>.

[70] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 17 and 19, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-38,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043105>.

[71] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 21 and 23, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-43,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043198>.

[72] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 25, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043228>.

• **Cornered Magic Squares**

[73] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.

[74] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.

[75] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.

• **Creative Magic Squares**

[76] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations, **Zenodo**, June 22, pp. 1-45, 2021,
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009224>.

[77] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations with Fraction Numbers Entries (Version 2), **Zenodo**,
August 16, 2021, 1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5209502>.